

LINLOSS

Data Collection Training Workshop - Summary Report

July 2nd–4th, 2025
Social Sciences Institute
IONTAS Building
Maynooth University

Table of Contents

03

ABOUT THE LINLOSS PROJECT

- Linloss Team
- Objectives of the Workshop

11

STUDY VISIT TO CARRICKMACROSS

04

WORKSHOP - DAY 1

- Introduction
- Analysis of Phase 1 of the Project
- Sampling and recruitment
- Ethical consideration

12

SUMMARY

07

WORKSHOP - DAY 2

- Unstructured interview
- Structured data collection
- Reflexive interview
- Participatory map

12

NEXT STEPS

10

WORKSHOP - DAY 3

- Review of previous day
- Data management and workflow
- Wrapping up

13

CONTACT DETAILS

About LINLOSS project

LINLOSS is a cross-national study that will compare experiences of social loss in two communities – one in Ireland and one in Poland between 2005 and 2025. The project aims to understand how what we leave behind affects future directions within our communities, families and individual lives. It will trace and explain patterns of social loss in the two study areas and will develop a formal theory of social loss.

The LINLOSS project was initiated in 2023, and it will be completed by 2028. The project is funded by the European Research Council Advanced Grant (Project 101098100). It is a collaboration between Maynooth University and University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland.

LINLOSS Team

The team is led by Prof. Jane Gray from Maynooth University, who is the Principal Investigator. The project partner is Dr. Witold Mandrysz from University of Silesia in Katowice. The researchers on the team are:

Dr. Siresa L. Berengueres, Senior Post-doctoral researcher

Dr. Milena Komarova, Post-doctoral researcher

Dr. Maria P. Waclawik, Post-doctoral researcher

The team also includes two research assistants:

Gabriela Styrkowicz, Research Assistant

Violetta Di Bucchianico, Research Assistant

and a post-graduate researcher, Saif Ali.

Objectives of the Workshop

The LINLOSS Data Collection Training Workshop was designed to support the planning of the second phase of the project and to prepare the team for the research activities involved.

Data collection for Phase 1 (selection and social mapping of the two study areas) is complete. Phase 2 (data collection with multi-generational families in each study area) will begin in October 2025.

The workshop provided essential information on the data collection process and training in the multi-modal research instruments to be used in Phase 2.

Participation in the workshop also provided an opportunity for an in-person meeting of the entire team and for sharing experiences of working on the project from both the Polish and Irish perspectives.

WORKSHOP - DAY 1

INTRODUCTION

Prof. Jane Gray opened the workshop and gave an overview of the sessions scheduled for the next three days and their goals. Professor Gray explained what to expect from the workshop, noting that the focus of this research training will be on Phase 2 data collection and the next steps. Before that, however, a summary of Phase 1 was presented.

REVIEW OF PHASE 1 OF THE PROJECT PROF. JANE GRAY

- The first session of the workshop was led by Prof. Gray, who summarised the project's progress to date and key milestones met, including the completion of 45 interviews with informants in Carrickmacross (20) and Suszec (25). Researchers who conducted these interviews in Poland and Ireland shared their fieldwork experiences, and the session provided an opportunity to compare the challenges they faced. They also discussed the processes of anonymisation and coding, which they have been working on.
- During the session, other accomplishments were also discussed, such as the collection of local history and other relevant materials for the planned community archives.
- Prof. Gray reviewed the steps required to complete the 1st Phase of the project,

which include the preparation of an openly available Study Protocol.

Additional written work will include a cross-national report based on national and regional indicators from existing data sources, as well as individual study reports for each study area. These will comprise an analysis of the social composition and patterns of social change within the study areas based on the research conducted for Phase 1. These final outputs from Phase 1 will enable the project to move into Phase 2 and are expected to be completed in the coming weeks. The team also discussed the need for bilingual preparation of selected research outputs.

The session concluded with the preparation of a plan to complete the remaining Phase 1 work, including deadlines for each key component.

SAMPLING AND RECRUITMENT

DR. MILENA KOMAROVA

Dr. Milena Komarova delivered a presentation on the sampling and recruitment strategies to be adopted in Phase 2. She explained the approach of *sampling for range*, which aims to maximise diversity. Families will be the unit of sampling in the LINLOSS project, which aims to interview members of two generations within multigenerational families (30 families/50 individuals within each study area).

Findings from Phase 1 will inform the sampling strategy by identifying the range of family types to be included. The team will ensure that families and individuals without current connections within the study areas will also be included.

- The session provided a chance to discuss different recruitment methods that will initiate Phase 2 of the project and potential challenges researchers may encounter. Several strategies for participant recruitment and community engagement were examined during the session. These included collaboration with local groups and organisations, outreach through local social media and more traditional media platforms, and the use of direct introductions by key contacts, among other approaches. Different ethical considerations related to the recruitment strategy were also reviewed.

- Significant attention was given to how to reach different members of the local community and to ensure the inclusion of a diverse group of interviewees representing various backgrounds and walks of life.
- The discussion highlighted similarities and differences between Carrickmacross and Suszec, with a focus on their unique social, historical, and cultural backgrounds. The team agreed on the importance of reassuring participants during the recruitment process that by sharing their stories, they will make a valuable contribution to community memory and local history, helping to preserve collective heritage.

The session allowed participants to exchange experiences related to recruiting participants and to review the logistics and practical considerations involved in planning a series of interviews in the study areas.

- The session concluded with a plan to develop a Recruitment Protocol, which will address the matters discussed and guide researchers through the recruitment process. This protocol will also include the planning of recruitment materials, such as posters and leaflets, for both in-person and online advertising.
- Dr. Komarova also shared relevant literature suggestions with the team.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

PROF. JANE GRAY

Prof. Jane Gray reviewed the key commitments outlined in the ethical approval document agreed with Maynooth University Research Ethics Committee, as well as the information and consent forms to be used during the fieldwork for Phase 2 of the project.

Prof. Gray explained the agreed ethical approach to working with vulnerable and non-vulnerable adults and discussed the challenges researchers may face while conducting interviews. The university's and European Research Council requirements and policies in this area were also mentioned.

- During the session, risks and mitigation strategies were analysed in detail. The team explored various scenarios related to interview conduct, addressing issues such as disclosures, confidentiality, privacy, and potential emotional difficulties.

Prof. Gray also explained the data protection requirements agreed with the Ethics Committees and Maynooth University Data Protection Office. She also proposed procedures to ensure the safety and protection of interviewees when conducting the research.

Key decisions and actions from Day 1 of the workshop included:

- Complete the following within the agreed timeframe:
 - Draft Phase 1 reports
 - Case study areas
 - Comparative analysis
 - Study protocol
 - Technical report
- Prepare Polish-language versions of relevant reports and summaries
- Develop the recruitment protocol
- Develop a recruitment and communication protocol

UNSTRUCTURED INTERVIEW

DR. MARIA P. WACLAWIK

Phase 2 of the LINLOSS project will include the collection of unstructured biographical interviews, formal data on life histories, genealogical support networks, and social values, and a follow up reflexive interview with each participant, which will conclude with the completion of a participatory map.

Dr. Maria P. Waclawik commenced Day 2 of the workshop with a presentation on "The Autobiographical Narrative Interview: Method and Practice," in which she reviewed both the theoretical foundations underpinning the unstructured interview, and practical aspects of the fieldwork. Based on the method developed by Fritz Schütze and its application in sociological studies, Dr. Waclawik explained the phases of the narrative interview process, which include: preparation Phase, Opening Question, Narrative Phase, Clarification and Reflection Phase (Post-narrative) and Closing Phase.

- To illustrate this, Dr. Waclawik presented examples from her fieldwork, in which she applied the autobiographical narrative interview method with participants from diverse backgrounds. Her research included individuals affected by political violence and historical trauma, among them Japanese American and Japanese Canadian survivors of WWII internment in the United States and Canada, as well as elders who had lived through WWII in Poland.
- The discussion that followed the presentation provided an opportunity to explore the practicalities and different scenarios likely to be encountered in the LINLOSS biographical interviews.

The team also discussed the role of the interviewer in the data collection process, including ethical considerations.

Dr. Waclawik highlighted the importance of the opening question for planning and conducting biographical narrative interviews. Together with the team, she discussed other key considerations, including preparation, ethical guidelines, equipment, technical aspects, and the surroundings and setting of the interview.

- Dr. Waclawik also shared tips for interviewers, containing useful suggestions for conducting effective interviews.

STRUCTURED DATA COLLECTION

DR. SIRESA L. BERENQUERES

Dr. Berengueres presented her work on the design and administration of the instruments for the collection of structured data. She walked the team through each of the planned sections of the structured questionnaire, designed to collect longitudinal data across a series of domains, such as occupations, residences, social support, and social values, among others. She also presented the Formr platform to the team, which will be used for the online collection of structured data, and described the design of a real time data visualisation tool that will serve to support the structured interview.

- Dr. Berengueres discussed practical aspects of the Formr platform, sharing helpful tips on how to be technically prepared to conduct computer-assisted personal interviews efficiently.
 - During the session, the team also discussed plans for conducting pilot interviews, which are scheduled to take place in the coming weeks.
-

REFLEXIVE INTERVIEW

PROF. JANE GRAY

DR. SIRESA L. BERENQUERES

The session focused on discussing the follow-up *reflexive interviews* that will be conducted in Phase 2 of the LINLOSS project.

Prof. Gray explained the principles behind the reflexive interview and described how this method allows participants to reflect on their life stories, elaborate on moments of change, and add any additional information they feel is important.

- The reflexive interview provides an opportunity for researchers to be accountable to research participants, based on visualizations of the data provided in their biographical interviews.

Prof. Gray also proposed some sample questions for opening and conducting the reflexive interviews. Various scenarios for conducting this type of interview were discussed with the team.

- Dr. Berengueres explained the design of the visual tool that will be used in the reflexive interviews. She elaborated on the process for constructing this tool which will take place between the first and the second stage of the interviewing process. The team discussed some of the challenges likely to be associated with building this tool.

Dr. Berengueres also explained the process for constructing the visualizations that will take place between the biographical and reflexive interviews. The team discussed some of the challenges likely to be associated with this process.

PARTICIPATORY MAP

PROF. JANE GRAY

DR. WITOLD MANDRYSZ

Dr. Mandrysz conducted a session on different approaches to participatory mapping in the social sciences and their application to the LINLOSS project. The session has been prepared in collaboration with Prof. Gray. After reviewing theoretical approaches to *mental mapping* and imaginary map elements and their practical applications, Dr. Mandrysz shared an example image of a mental map, emphasising the importance of such maps in the analysis of social relations and social spaces.

Dr. Mandrysz also explained the process of *sketch mapping*, in which participants are asked to mark areas of significance on base maps provided by the interviewer. He outlined its benefits, and noted that, for the purposes of this research, participants will be asked, after completing their reflexive interviews, to annotate maps of places that are important to them, including those that are no longer there.

Finally, Dr. Mandrysz highlighted the community dimension of mapping and discussed with the team the technical aspects of the mapping process, including relevant software tools for this method of data collection.

Key decisions and actions from Day 2 of the workshop included:

- Make a proposal on the opening question for the biographical interview
- Revise the support genealogy questionnaire
- Design visualisations linking the biographical and reflexive interviews
- Schedule pilot interviews
- Decide the final details on the implementation of the participatory map
- Review data handling practicalities across the data collection process

REVIEW OF PREVIOUS DAY PROF. JANE GRAY

The session, led by Prof. Gray, provided the team with an opportunity to discuss and address any outstanding issues from topics covered during the workshop, as well as to review various scenarios that may arise during Phase 2 of the project in both the Polish and Irish contexts.

The team discussed and agreed that several supporting materials and tools will be needed for the next stage of the project, including protocols and guidelines such as a Sampling and Recruitment Protocol, a Protocol for Research Data, and a Protocol for the community collections. It was also agreed that a Manual for Researchers will be developed to guide them in conducting interviews. This will be accompanied by other materials and communication tools to support participant recruitment and community outreach. These will include an Interviewer Pack and communication materials such as an information leaflet and posters.

The Interviewer Pack will consist of the recruitment protocol, an interview guide, hard copies of relevant questionnaires, a checklist, and information about the community collections.

The team also discussed the practical aspects of fieldwork related to data collection in both Poland and Ireland, including the challenges researchers may encounter in each context. Additionally, the group emphasised the importance of using plain language in documentation and addressed other practical matters relevant to the next phase, such as ethical, technical and logistical considerations.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND WORKFLOW PROF. JANE GRAY

Prof. Gray presented and reviewed the data management protocols applicable to Phase 2 of the project and explained the potential risks associated with data management at this stage. The transfer and storage of data, which bring particular challenges, were discussed as key elements in the data collection process.

During the session, the team reviewed the consent forms and discussed the challenges participants may face in completing them, particularly in relation to providing consent for the use of their data in archives. Different methods for ensuring data security were considered, along with how to effectively explain transcription, anonymisation, and data handling to participants.

Prof. Gray also presented the process for incorporating data into the MAXQDA software, along with an overview of data handling, workflow, and the platform's teamwork functions. Various challenges related to personal data and GDPR compliance were also addressed.

WRAPPING UP

During the last session, the LINLOSS team reviewed the plans for pilot interviews and the schedule of activities until the end of the year. An initial deadline calendar to complete agreed tasks was developed. Details regarding planned publications and supportive materials for Phase 2 of the project were also finalised.

Key decisions and actions from Day 3 of the workshop included:

- Create a manual for researchers
- Develop supplementary materials and offline forms for researchers
- Finalise workflow and division of tasks
- Review data handling and storage protocols

STUDY VISIT TO CARRICKMACROSS

On the first day of training, the LINLOSS team visited Carrickmacross, one of the project's study areas. The visit included a walk around the town and a talk by Dr. Komarova about important places in the area. After that, the team visited the Carrickmacross Workhouse Visitor & Community Centre, where, guided by a tour guide, they learned about the history of the site and the significance of the workhouse in Irish history.

The team had the opportunity to learn about the background behind the creation of workhouses in Ireland by British authorities before and during the 1840s Great Famine.

They also heard personal stories of the workhouse's residents and the struggles they faced both before and after arriving there.

Additionally, the team heard about the impact that workhouses had on individuals, families, society, and how they contributed to population changes and emigration.

SUMMARY

The three-day LINLOSS Data Collection Training Workshop, held at Maynooth University, provided the team with training in developing and applying the methods planned for Phase 2 of the project. This included:

- conducting biographical and reflexive interviews,
- working with the questionnaire to collect formal data,
- using sketch mapping techniques,
- covering various aspects related to transcription, anonymisation, data handling, and the importance of archiving,
- ethical considerations throughout the data collection process.

Discussions during the sessions helped the team identify the necessary supportive resources, materials, and tools that will guide researchers throughout the data collection process. The workshop also provided an opportunity to discuss interview techniques and receive hands-on training in using the questionnaire and associated software. The in-person training was valuable for strengthening team collaboration and improving workflow. It also enabled the team to establish next steps and assign responsibilities to each team member in order to move the project forward.

Funded by the European Union (ERC, Linloss, Project No. 101098100). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

NEXT STEPS

Based on team feedback and the LINLOSS programme of work, a list of next steps covering different areas of the project was developed and organised by level of urgency. Key priorities include:

- completing the coding and analysis for Phase 1,
- finalising a publication of the research protocol for Phase 2, to be submitted to an academic journal,
- revising the questionnaire,
- finalising the details of the biographical and reflexive interviews,
- preparing a set of supportive materials for researchers for Phase 2,
- planning the pilot interviews,
- the participant recruitment campaign.

The team meets online on a weekly basis, which allows for the implementation of agreed actions and ensures steady progress on the project in an efficient manner.

LINLOSS

Contact details:

The LINLOSS project
Maynooth University Social Sciences Institute
Iontas Building, North Campus,
Maynooth University,
Maynooth, County Kildare, Ireland
Eircode: W23 NPY6

+353 1 708 3350

HOME - LINLOSS

Linloss@mu.ie

LINLOSS | MAYNOOTH | FACEBOOK

